

WHAT DOES NANOCELLULOSE DO TO THE PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES?

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ABSTRACT

Hierarchical composites containing loose flax fibres, bacterial cellulose and polypropylene or polylactic acid were produced to study the effect of nanocellulose on the composites. The composites were manufactured using a wet route, to ensure that the nanocellulose hornification occurred throughout the entire composite. The effect of nanocellulose network was seen on the composite morphology and its strength. When using polypropylene as matrix, the nanocellulose addition did not affect their mechanical properties. However, when using polylactic acid, the composite properties considerably improved.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre composites received renewed interest in the past years. The advantages of natural fibres, such as their biodegradability, abundance and non-health risk, play a competitive role on their future uses. Natural fibre composites are a great example of how renewable materials can be utilized in competitive structural materials [1]. The performance of natural fibre composites is determined by the fibre quality (due to processing and agricultural factors), their fibre volume fraction, their distribution within the matrix and of course, the stress transfer between matrix and fibres [2]. Lots of effort has been spent to overcome these drawbacks, such as chemical modification of natural fibres or the matrix, to enhance their adhesion within the composite. Another way of enhance the properties of natural fibre composites is by using fillers or binders, such as nanocellulose. There are two different approaches to produce nanocellulose. The first one, the top-down approach, consists of obtaining nanocellulose from lignocellulosic materials by mechanical or chemical procedures [3]. The fibrils obtained by these methods, are not pure cellulose fibrils but also contain other constituents, such as lignin and hemicellulose, which are naturally present in the natural fibre structure. The bottom up approach, utilizes bacteria, such as *Acetobacter xylinum*, to produce pure cellulose fibrils as an extracellular product [4].

The importance of nanocellulose comes from the fact that it can form a strong and irreversible network structure by forming strong irreversible hydrogen bonds upon drying. This process is called hornification [5]. Because this process occurs when water evaporates from the composite, this is not a problem when working with nanopapers [6] but it is when working with polymers, so manufacturing methods need to be taken into account. Although efforts have been made to try to introduce nanocellulose fillers, it does not enable a homogeneous network formation [7]. We have been working on a way to introduce the nanocellulose homogeneously into composites via a wet route, by

manufacturing a preform prior to the matrix inclusion by infusion, which considerably enhances the mechanical properties of the final composite [8, 9].

This processing method only works when the matrix can be added afterwards (mostly thermoset matrixes). In the case of thermoplastic polymers, such as polypropylene (PP) or polylactic acid (PLA), commonly used engineering matrixes, this manufacturing method cannot be used and neither can methods such as injection molding, where the nanocellulose network cannot be formed in a homogenous way throughout the composite. However, these composites can be manufactured by compression moulding emulating a paper-making process. By working with loose natural and polymer fibres, the nanocellulose can hornify throughout the fibres prior to the melting of the polymer leading to a hierarchical structure.

Here we demonstrate the effect of bacterial cellulose on the properties of hierarchical composites produced by co-filtration of bacterial cellulose, flax fibres and PP or PLA fibres followed by compression moulding.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The natural fibres used within the composites were flax fibres kindly supplied by S.A.R.L. Novalin, France. The nanocellulose used as reinforcement was bacterial cellulose, which was obtained from a commercially available dessert, nata de coco (CHAOKOH coconut gel in syrup, Ampol Food Processing Ltd., Nakorn Pathom, Thailand) and extracted following previously reported methods [10]. The sodium hydroxide used for the bacterial cellulose purification was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Polypropylene fibres were kindly supplied by Schwarzwälder Textil-Werke (STW) and polylactic acid fibres by MiniFIBERS Inc.

2.2 Composite manufacturing

The composite manufacturing started by dispersing a predetermined amount of wet bacterial cellulose in water and by adding dry-blended polymer and flax fibres. The dry-commingled fibres were dispersed in water and left to soak overnight. The dispersion was then vacuum co-filtrated emulating a paper making process. The remaining water of the wet preform was removed by cold compression and it was consolidated under 2t at 175 °C; to allow the melting of the polymer followed by annealing at 120°C. On the composites with PP, the amount of PP varied with the amount of bacterial cellulose, maintaining a constant 40% wt. flax content. Due to the manufacturing method used, the PLA composites contained 40% wt. PLA.

2.3 Characterization of composites

The tensile strength of the composites was studied by using an Instron universal testing machine (Instron 5969, Instron GmbH, Germany). The tests were carried out w1kN or 50kN load cell (depending on the specimen's strength) and at 1mm/min. To have a representative value, a minimum of 5 specimens were tested for each set of samples. The testing specimen's dimensions were around 80 x 15 x 2 mm (the thickness varied with the fibre content).

The morphological structure of the natural fibre composites was studied by Scanning Electron Microscopy (JEOL JCM-6000). The accelerating voltage used for the characterization was 15kV. The polypropylene and polylactic acid composites were fixed with the help of carbon tabs to the sample holders and then coated at 80 mA for 1 min, to ensure sufficient electrical conductivity. Relevant parts of the composites were selected to ensure a good comparison.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile strength of the composites

The tensile strength of the composites is presented in Figure 1. The addition of bacterial cellulose on the composites containing flax and PP negatively affects the tensile strength. The quantity added to the composites does not show any significant improvement on the properties, which means that the bacterial cellulose network, itself, is hindering the composites' consolidation. There are two possible

causes. The first one is that the nanocellulose hornification cannot take place as a result of a lack of contact points to form the network, due to the presence of flax and un-melted polypropylene fibres. The second option, would be that once the hornification has occur, the nanocellulose network difficults/blocks the polymer melting flow.

Figure 1: Effect of bacterial cellulose on the properties of PLA/flax and PP/flax composites.

However, the addition of bacterial cellulose to the PLA composites shows a significant increase of the tensile strength of the composites. If the un-melted polymer fibres would difficult the bacterial cellulose formation, the composites tensile strength would show the same behavior for PP and PLA. Since this is not happening, it can be conclude that the nanocellulose network, which is formed after water evaporation (at around 100°C), its obstructing the melting flow of the polymer (because the melting of the polymer takes place at 163°C PP and at 165°C for PLA). Since PLA is more polar than polypropylene, the fibre melt impregnates the network entailing the expected reinforcement. Previous research reported an increase on tensile strength of 70% with the addition of 10% of bacterial cellulose (respect to the wt. % natural fibres, which corresponds approximately to a 6% addition to the total composite) [8, 9]. The increase of the tensile strength for PLA composites was 128 % and 295 % for 6% and 10% wt. bacterial cellulose, respectively.

3.1 Morphology of composites

The effect of the bacterial cellulose network on the morphology of the flax fibre composites was also different for the polypropylene and polylactic acid matrices. The morphological features of the PLA composites containing bacterial cellulose were different to the composites without the additional reinforcement. In Figure 2, the fractured surface after tensile tests from these composites can be seen.

Figure 2: Image of PLA/flax composite with and without BC (right and left respectively).

In Figure 3 these differences can be seen in more detail. The image of the fractured surface of the PLA composite without bacterial cellulose was not possible to be seen under SEM (Figure 3 [left]) due to the scattering produced by the loose flax fibres. Figure 3 [right] shows the fractured surface of the composite containing bacterial cellulose. It can be seen that the PLA distribution throughout the composite and its surface is different for the composite containing bacterial cellulose, which suggests that the nanocellulose network is acting as a flow medium or melt support, allowing a controlled distribution of the melted fibres through the composite.

Figure 3: Morphology differences between PLA/flax composite without and with 10% BC (left and right column respectively).

When using PP as a matrix, no difference can be appreciated on the SEM images between the composites with and without nanocellulose, as it can be seen in figure 4. Bacterial cellulose fibrils cannot be observed in the images as they are on the nanoscale, which makes them difficult to view at these magnifications and they only represent 10% of the composite.

Figure 4: Morphology differences between PP/Flax composite without and with 10% BC (left and right column respectively).

4 CONCLUSIONS

Natural fibre PP or PLA composites containing bacterial cellulose as an additional reinforcement were successfully manufactured via a wet processing route, which enabled the hornification of the nanocellulose in a controlled way through the entire composites' area. In the case of the composites with PP as a matrix, the addition or not of bacterial cellulose did negatively affect the composite properties, due to the fact that the nanocellulose network formed upon water removal blocks afterwards the polymer fibres melt. This however, was not observed when using nanocellulose as a further reinforcement for PLA composites. The tensile strength increases 128%, 295% and 460% when using 6, 10 and 20% wt. bacterial cellulose, respectively. In this case, the bacterial cellulose network was acting as a flow medium allowing a controlled melting of the polymer through the composites, due to PLA polar groups and low viscosity (compared to PP). The effect of bacterial cellulose in PLA composites could also be seen on its morphological features. The images shown of the composites containing bacterial cellulose suggested that a more even distribution of the polymer and a better adhesion is achieved when using bacterial cellulose. Although the composites containing PP did not exhibit any enhancement on their tensile strength behavior, it expands the possibilities of the preform manufacturing, since once the network is formed (but the polymer not melted), the polymer and flax fibres are kept in place by the nanocellulose network. The handling of the preform becomes then an advantage to be taken into account, for example when draping composites.

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